

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

CHARITABLE ACTIVITIES OF PUBLIC ORGANIZATIONS IN KARS DURING THE FIRST WORLD WAR: KARS COMMITTEE

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Abstract

The article is dedicated to the activities of public organizations in the Kars region, the hottest area on the Caucasus Front in the First World War, where heavy military operations were conducted between Russia and Türkiye. The issues of charitable activities of public organizations in Kars region are highlighted on the basis of primary sources and rich archival materials. At the moment, when migration problems are increasing in the region and also in the world, and the waves of refugees are intensifying as a result of destructive wars, there is a need to further expand the traditions of charity. In this regard, the article is of scientific importance and is of great relevance in terms of looking at the historical processes in the South Caucasus region during the First World War, studying the historical roots of Türkiye-Azerbaijan relations, which are based on strategic friendship and fraternal relations.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, First World War, Türkiye, Russia, Caucasian Front, Kars Committee, public organizations, refugees, charity

Introduction. Beginning of the First World War, as in all territories of Russia, caused great repercussion in Azerbaijan too. Some important extreme measures were implemented by state and government organs connected with the beginning of the war. All forces were mobilized.

Results and discussion: Historical facts related to this topic have been covered to a certain extent in a number of scientific works on historiography and have been involved in research work. [15; 16 ;17; 18; 19; 20; 21; 22; 23; 24]. In 1914, on July 23, immediately after the declaration of war, a meeting of the Baku City Duma was convened. At the meeting, the City Duma decided to hold the following events related to the outbreak of war:

1. People from both sexes should be accepted to give medical assistance to ill and wounded people brought to hospitals and in fight regions;

2. 100.000 rouble should be issued from stock capital to implement this aim. City office should appoint advocate to this work. Special commission consisted of 3-5 people from City Office deputies should be organized;

3. Free nurse and doctor's assistant course (theoretical and practical) attached to Mikhaylovski hospital for 6 weeks should be organized. For this purpose, 2.000 rubles were put [1].

Measures connected with the beginning of the war were implemented not only by state and government organs, but also by social organizations worked in Baku. Among these organizations, large scale activities of "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" had great importance.

Society began to carry out some projects connected with beginning of the war. Various measures connected with the opening of hospitals for ill and wounded moslem soldiers, implementing of "Brother

aid" project, organizing of the aid work to war sufferers and turk moslem refugees in Gars province have been carried out. We will deal with it in detail in the other divisions of the monograph. Other Azerbaijan national-public organization, "Baku Moslem Women Charitable Society" also had important activities in this field.

The "Challenge" that women society did for involving all moslems at the same time, had great historical importance from the standpoint of directing people and helping to war sufferers and turk refugee moslem population in Gars. We introduce this touching challenge to readers as it is: "Kind, sirs! While you're leading a peaceful and happy life, there are many hungry, abandoned, orphan family at that time. Look, these defenseless, abandoned women are also your sisters. You should feel their material and spiritual blow too. While enjoying yourselves in society with your wives, friends, imagine that there your unhappy sisters in Gars. Your hungry, frozen sisters. Think, that they had families, children, and joys too. But now they are helpless in forests and mountains. Give your hands to your sisters. Mothers! Think that, while you are pampering your lovely children, there are hungry, frozen infants who have become orphans. Give your hands to them and don't go of their hands till the end of their life. Dear children, cherished children! While you are lying in your warm, clean bed, think that your brothers and sisters suffer from starvation and cold. Regret to their situation, put aside something from daily expense and help poor children with a loaf of bread. Now an opportunity arose and we help to sufferers for humanism's and Moslems' sake! Feel your being truly Moslems and help brothers! [7].

A response to this call came from all over place of Azerbaijan! This response was a sign of nobody's denying their property to help them: Ladies, from Goychay, Diyeli village, Siyare khanum, Zeynab khanum

and Sakina khanum Afandiyevs wrote following letter to Rahila khanum Hacibayova, the head of "Baku Moslem Women Charitable Society": "We are very touched from Gars events written in the newspaper pages. Our moslem sisters' and brothers' tragic fate awakes a great feeling of regret in us. We can not explain our senses by anything. We are sending 17 Rouble to you on our Moslem sisters' behalf." [4].

During the First World War strong there were great destructions in the Gars province, ten thousands of people became refugees, thousands patronizing orphan children and giving them initial and sustainable material, spiritual help arose. As it's known, at that time and before many areas, including Azerbaijan was in bondage of Russia. In the years of First World War the Azerbaijanis had to choose: to turn against to Turks by supporting patron countries, Russian's war policy against Türkiye or help to Turks with whom they had the same religion, language and root. In this situation, by choosing right and courageous way without thinking any policy, they acted against patron country's policy and helped their nation in this hard time. Azerbaijan prominent intellectuals turned Russian's supreme platforms into battle ground. Each possible step was taken in this way. The settlement of the population who were imposed to destructions and helping them took important place in the measures that "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" carried out in this field during the war years.

In January, 1915, province governor Podqurski wrote a telegram to the chairman of the «Baku Moslem Charitable Society», Mirza Asadullayev connected with situation in Gars with the call for helping to war sufferer moslems. In the telegram it was written: "Moslem population of the Gars province are worried about the war. The situation is terrible. There is no help from any place. I am appealing to the society (Baku Moslem Charitable Society-N.M) for aid-governor Podqurski" [9]. After this appeal extraordinary meeting of administrative personnel of the "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" was called connected with exactly this problem. In the meeting by discussing the organizing work of urgent help to war sufferer Moslems and Turks in Gars province it was decided that: "Gars Moslems heavy situation was confirmed by Governor's official call. Now we are before our national duty. Population did not believe in coming 17 refugees to Baku. Society has to deal with this big urgent problem" [5].

In the same meeting special appeal to all Azerbaijanis was accepted. This call of the administrative personnel of the "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" was published in all press organs. In the appeal it is said: "As it's known, Moslem population of Gars province suffer from military events. Hunger and cold are everywhere. Urgently needs help. According to words of the member of State Duma Mammad Yusif Jafarov, in the places people have no bread and other foodstuffs, so people eat barley flour, but it has scarce stock. Urgent clothes and money are demanded. Gars governor colonel Podqurski asked from the society about that. Society has got permission to collect money and clothes from local population.. Taking into consideration all above mentioned "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" calls

everybody to take part in this well-wisher work for helping to Moslem sufferers from war. Money is accepted in the offices of local newspapers, and in the office of the Asadullayev's company, but objects are accepted, in the office where "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" locates. Kind men, please, help. Each coin is valuable." [11].

There were appeals from all over regions where Turk Moslems lived to help to "Baku Moslem Charitable Society". In the first heavy months of the war, in January, 1915, head of the military office over Türkiye provinces addressed to the administrative personnel of the society. It was asked to help to Moslem-Turk population of many villages in Meloselsk whose homes were destroyed during the battles. In the information given by the head of the military office over Türkiye regions to the society it was stated that". Melekyankur village has been imposed to terrible destructions.

There are 15 homes with 60 inhabitants...These inhabitants are olds, women and infants. During the war these people had to leave their homes because of the destructions that the bullets and projectiles had caused. After the war's calming down, when people returned here homes had been ruined. Countrymen want to stay in these houses by reconstructing them. Women have made places with dark and soil ground. We ask "Moslem Charitable Society" to help this village." [3].

It was also asked to send food, clothes, and bed things to Shikashar village which was in the same situation with Melekyankur in the appeal of head of military office over Türkiye regions [3].

On January 3, 1915, just after this appeal, in «İsmailiyye» building joint meeting of the administrative personnel of "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" and the department of society on helping Moslems suffered from war" was held. In the meeting, the matter of supporting helping to Moslem turks suffering from horrors of war, driven out of their native lands, on the other hand remained homeless in their native village, was discussed. It was decided to accept appeal to the tsar's special governor in Caucasus about giving help to Moslem turks suffering from the war. [6]. Special commission consisting of prominent intellectuals and influential persons was formed with the aim of presenting the appeal personally to the governor and at the same time getting permission for organizing aid collecting work from all over the Caucasus to moslem turks suffering from the war. The following persons were included into the commission: former deputy of State Duma, lawyer Alimardan Topchibashov, real adviser Fatalikhan Khoisky, society ember Huseyn Taghiyev and deputy of Baku City Duma Aghabala Guliyev. So, with this structure commission have gone to Tiflis for carrying on concrete negotiations [6].

Azerbaijan delegation's negotiations with Caucasus governor gave showed positive result. As a response to this appeal governor signed order. According to this order «Baku Moslem Charitable Society» was allowed to collect money and objects from local people to help war sufferers [10].

In stead of this, society should regularly report to City head on aid collecting work [10]. After a while this order was substituted with new one. So, according to

the order signed by Caucasian governor, society was again allowed for war sufferer moslems to use Caucasian border [14]. The difference between these two orders was that while the first order considered the organization of help work for only Baku province, the second considered this work for all Caucasian borders. The second one was more different and important with its large scope.

In March, 1915 the committee of "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" on Gars province was formed. On March 16, in the same year, province committee's meeting on helping to sufferers from war in Gars. In the meeting deputy of the Russia State Duma Mammad Yusif Jafarov raised a question about opening of the official committee of the "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" recognized by the government in Gars. This offer was approved by participants of meeting. In that meeting it was decided to form such committees of the "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" in Ardahan, Sarigamish and Kagizman circles [12].

But it is clear that forming of committees the Gars province had to be carried out by the official permission of the central administrative organs. In accordance with this, Mammad Yusif Jafarov by sending the telegram to the administrative personnel of the "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" stated that "Tiflis should be informed about this problem. Sending of the representatives of the "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" on an official trip to the province and province committees should be permitted." [12].

Connected with the above mentioned case, in March, 1915 the meeting of the "Department on Moslems suffered from war" of the "Baku Moslem Charitable Society" was held. In meeting elections to the Gars committee were discussed. It was decided doctor Khosrov Pasha Bay Sultanov and Aslan bay Safikurdski from Yelizavetpol to be elected as representative to Gars province committee [13]. The main function of these representatives as commissioners of the society was to form aid work to war sufferers. According to the common consent, Gars was considered to be representatives' place [13]. Representatives had also to go to those places and form special groups to help. In their turn, the main purpose of forming groups was the distribution of food and other necessary things [12].

During the talks between Mammad Yusif Jafarov, member of the society, deputy of Russia State Duma and Podqorski, Governor of Gars province, colonel, Podqorski gave his consent to support the works that representatives would do. So, on the March 17, 1915, representatives elected by the society went to Gars [13]. After some months, in November, 1915 one more representative- Rashid bay Akhundzadeh was elected to the province committee. He was appointed as a second assistant of commissioner (Khosrov Pasha bay Sultanov-N.M.). Despite of measures taken for systematic organization of aid work to war suffered Moslems and Turks, from the point of national view Turks' foes made trouble in this proses [13].

The structure of the Gars province committee on helping to war sufferers in Caucasus front was considered in the following way. The colonel of the Gars

province and representatives of three nations-Armenians, Moslems and Greeks were included to this structure [8].

As in all legislative legal committees, in Gars province committee also problems were settled by the majority of votes. Sometimes committee had to make unfair decisions when Armenians' and Greeks' interests overlapped in some cases, specially in national ones. This caused dissatisfaction of not only committee member Azerbaijanis but also all Azerbaijanis who worked in this sphere. In November, 1915, in the meeting of Gars province committee, such a decision was passed that province committee refused to help refugees from Türkiye, including women and children, forming vast majority. In accordance with this, in the meeting, member of "Baku Moslem Charitable Society", Alikhan Kantemirov petitioned for rehearing this case. Alikhan Kantemirov gave sound facts about this matter's being

against the laws passed by the government. These facts stated that, in the first chapter of the law about refugees passed on August 30, 1915 it was written that refugees were peoples who were deported from military operation districts by the order of military authority, who fled their homes or were driven out. Another fact made by Alikhan Kantemirov was about the article 6 of the same law: "According to accepted regulation refugees are given help by the government. Germans and Hungarians are exceptions. From here it is clear that giving help to refugees from Türkiye was not forbidden. Only after this clear explanation, the province committee decided to appeal to the tsar's governor in Caucasian to rehear this problem [8]. Then, as we mentioned above, Governor signed special order connected with giving aid to war suffer and refugee Turk Moslems. So, there would be no any obstacle in this way.

Conclusions: The First World War, as one of the manifestations of the civilizational crisis, plunged humanity into a hitherto unprecedented humanitarian catastrophe – refugee. This phenomenon has received a special scope on the Eastern Front, and in particular in the Russian Empire. During the First World War, charity events in the regions near the military operations on the Caucasian Front played a decisive role in saving the population from hunger and cold.

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